

Oral Maxillofacial Surgery

3-D Printing in Oral & Maxillofacial Surgery

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The reconstructions of oro-cranio-maxillofacial complex defects are often a tedious task because of versatility of tissue types within a small region. As future's perspective is envisioned towards personalized delivery of care that is patient specific the agenda of “one size fits all” is vanishing. The three dimensional (3-D) printing may pave a way for on-demand and patient specific reconstructs with complex shapes and high performance in the field of oral and maxillofacial surgery. A multidisciplinary team of surgeons, engineers and scientists should work together to fulfil the vision to repair, regenerate, and reconstruct dental, oral and craniofacial hard and soft tissues.

From the past to present, the humans used “subtractive approaches” such as casting, molding, forming etc., in which a solid block of material is reduced to a desirable form to construct the desired object which leads to subsequent advances and in the field thereby increasing the reconstruct efficiency. Back in 1970's where 3-D imaging techniques such as Magnetic Resonance Imaging(MRI) and Computed Tomography (CT) revolutionized the usage of CAD/CAM system, the present day imaging techniques will help us reconstruct tissue substitutes based on acquired 3D anatomical data. Major breakthrough was in mid-1980 where 3D corporation technology introduced the concept of Additive Manufacturing (AM) replacing subtractive approach and since then it finds its application in various fields such as aerospace, automobile, medicine and dentistry.

3D printing refers to a set of AM methods which fabricate constructs in layer by layer mode, which permit rapid fabrication of 3D constructs with fine details from various materials such as metals, polymers, ceramics, composites, and biological materials like hydrogels. To make a desired 3D printed constructs for oral and maxillofacial surgery for both hard and soft tissue defects appropriate printing material is required.

There is an extensive range of 3D printing methods which has potential applications in oral and maxillofacial surgery which are stereolithography (SLA), selective laser sintering (SLS), fused

deposition modeling (FDM), photopolymer jetting (PPJ), and powder binder printing (PBP).

3D printed membrane made by alginate – BFP1 (right) and the 3D printing machine used for its fabrication (left)

Pre operative mesh positioning & stabilization using stereolithographic model

3D CT image of a patients skull representing the large frontal cranial defects. The real sized 3D printed skull model with the HA implant fitted at the defect site.

Pre contouring of titanium mesh on the 3D printed model

Schematic representation of the 3D Bioprinting concept

S. No.	3D PRINTING METHODS	APPLICATIONS
1	Stereolithography (SLA)	1. Anatomical orofacial models 2. Surgical guides and templates 3. Dental restorations
2	Selective laser sintering (SLS)	1. Maxillofacial anatomic models 2. Patient-specific dental implants 3. Tissue engineering scaffolds
3	Fused deposition modeling (FDM)	1. Reconstructive mandibular models 2. Repair of facial fractures 3. Anatomic models to repair complicated cranial defects 4. Accurate diagnosis & treatment planning in challenging implant surgeries
4	Powder binder printing (PBP)	1. Bone tissue engineering scaffolds 2. Complex-shaped prostheses 3. Mandibular models

3D Bio printing-An alternate dimension?

Also known as cell-laden printing is the soft and hard tissue reconstruction of defects in cranio-maxillofacial region by computer aided printing of human living cells with bio-ink being a collection of human cells, biomaterials and biomolecules. Some of the methods include inkjet, micro-extrusion, and laser-assisted bioprinting. 3D bioprinting is used to reconstruct bone and cartilage insitu but has certain drawbacks like sensitive surgical handling, difficulty in storage and shipping, less shelf life.

3D printed medical modelling

Also called as biomodelling, refers to fabrication of real size anatomic models with data obtained from medical images. The most common applications in oral and maxillofacial region includes management of tooth impaction, removal of fused roots,

dental auto-transplantation surgeries, as TMJ models, mandibular models, face and skull models. Since medical models are real sized models, it allows for exact determination of position and dimension of defects along with corrective intervention with minimum invasiveness for surrounding tissues.

3D printing and Dental instruments

Apart from these, 3D printing finds its application in maxillofacial region in production of dental instruments – including surgical guides, splints, crown and dentures, oral and maxillofacial implants and total jaw prostheses.

3D printing and fabrication of multi and interfacial defects

Recently, 3D printing also plays an important role in fabrication of heterogenous constructs such as osteomucosal, osteochondral and periodontal tissues as well as dentin/pulp complex in a whole tooth. Despite the advances, its clinical implications in oral and maxillofacial region requires further investigation.

In conclusion, AM models are useful tools in fabrication of oral and maxillofacial reconstructs with a view of opening a wide array of scope in the field of reconstructive surgery. Although these models produce constructs with considerable resolution, high resolution reconstructs are still a long way out which requires an opinion from operating surgeons whether it is required or not as it takes more time to print and without sacrificing the strength, handleability and shape of final constructs especially in custom fit implants. One of the advantages include it eliminates the need of animal studies. 3D printing is certainly a boon to the oral and maxillofacial surgery which takes patients life style and health care to next level beyond our thoughts.